

Integrated germplasm improvement—rainfed lowland

Shakuntla; a rice variety for rainfed lowlands in Bihar, India

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Shakuntla (RAU73-16-1-40) was released in 1995 for cultivation in rainfed lowland areas of Bihar, India. Rainfed lowland rice is grown on about 40% (2.2 million ha) of the state's area. The current yield averages less than 1.0 t ha⁻¹.

Developed from the cross Pankaj/Br8, Shakuntla is weakly photoperiod-sensitive, of long duration (140-145 d), and is medium in height. Its grains are long and slender.

In the All India coordinated yield trials, Shakuntla ranked fifth in 1990 and first in 1991. In state uniform variety trials during 1993 and 1994, Shakuntla yielded 12.3-50.5% more than check Mahsuri. In the 1994 eastern India rainfed lowland shuttle breeding trial, the variety was tested using normal planting with 30-d-old seedlings and delayed planting with 60-d-old seedlings. The yield advantage was greater under normal than delayed planting (Table 1).

From 1988 to 1990, Shakuntla outperformed check Mahsuri by an average of 20% under direct seeding and transplanting (Table 2). ■

Table 1. Grain yield of Shakuntla at different sites in India. 1990-94.

Year	Site	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)		LSD (5%)	CV (%)
		Shakuntla	Mahsuri or Utkal prabha		
1990	Pusa	2.2	1.4	0.9	27.1
	Sabour	3.1	2.4	1.0	15.0
	Chinsurah	2.7	2.6	0.4	10.9
	Ghaghraghat	2.2	1.2	0.5	7.1
1991	Ranital	3.4	2.8	0.4	8.1
	Canning	2.8	2.1	0.5	10.8
	Patna	2.5	1.4	0.6	15.3
	Pusa	2.6	2.2	0.3	7.9
1993	Patna	4.1	3.4	0.1	24.0
	Pusa	2.8	2.6	ns ^a	
	Sabour	1.7	1.1	0.8	23.3
1994	Patna	4.8	3.9	0.1	16.3
	Pusa	2.7	1.7	0.6	16.2
	Sabour	1.9	0.5	0.8	20.8
	Bikramganj	4.6	3.3	0.5	5.7
1994			<i>Normal planting with 30-d-old seedlings</i>		
	Chinsurah	3.0	3.4	0.4	10.7
	Masodha	6.5	5.0	0.9	9.0
	Patna	5.2	6.7	0.2	17.4
	Pusa	5.5	3.0	0.5	6.9
	Raipur	2.8	2.3	0.7	27.9
	Titabar	5.5	3.4	0.9	13.5
			<i>Delayed planting with 60-d-old seedlings</i>		
	Chinsurah	5.1	3.3	0.6	9.3
	Masodha	2.5	2.1	1.0	27.6
	Patna	3.6	2.2	0.3	6.4
	Pusa	2.2	1.3	0.2	32.1
	Raipur	4.6	2.2	ns ^a	
	Titabar	2.6	2.2	ns ^a	
	Pooled mean	3.5	2.6		

^a ns = not significant.

Table 2. Grain yield (t ha⁻¹) of Shakuntla in farmers' fields under direct seeding and transplanting. ICAR-IRRI collaborative research, 1988-90 wet seasons.

Variety	Direct seeding 1988-90	Transplanting 1989-90	Av	Increase over check (%)
Shakuntla	3.5	3.7	3.6	20
Mahsuri (check)	2.9	3.0	3.0	

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